

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Slurry Concentrator to reduce transport costs

Challenge

In regions with high livestock density, there is an imbalance between the volume of nutrients generated and the farmland available for their application.

Aims

To separate manure into two phases: a semi-liquid phase (concentrating the majority of the organic matter and nutrients) to be transported and applied to distant fields where nutrients are not available; and a liquid phase (with a low nutrient concentration) to be applied in a nearby field.

Rationale

The differentiated management of the two phases is designed to minimise transport costs and optimise the application of nutrients to the soil from the agronomic and environmental perspectives.

Results

The proposed innovative system produces two liquid fractions, one with high concentrations of nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus) and the other with low concentrations. As a result, the concentrated effluent can be more efficiently transported and applied to any farmland, while the diluted effluent can be used on surrounding fields.

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CONCENTRATED FRACTION

Optimal for transportation to distant areas, as it takes up less volume while containing the majority of nutrients.

DILUTED FRACTION

Applied in nearby fields, characterised by a higher volume and lower nutrient concentration.

View of the concentrator

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our journey!

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